

STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES ON THE USE OF SEMESTA (SOURCE OF ENGLISH MATERIALS USING TECHNOLOGY-BASED APPLICATION) IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' ENGLISH SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to discover hospitality management students' perspectives on using SEMESTA to improve their English skills. This study used a mixed method with a quantitative and qualitative approach. The study's respondents included 35 students of Bachelor of Applied Hospitality Management, Faculty of Vocational Studies, Universitas Brawijaya. Data were collected from questionnaires and interview guidelines. The study's findings showed that the SEMESTA (Source of English Materials Using Technology-based Application) website as a medium for learning English for Hospitality Management students is easily accessible by all devices. However, there have also been instances of website buffering when respondents used the SEMESTA website. Furthermore, respondents' perspectives on English learning materials on the SEMESTA website showed that the material presented complies with their needs and is appropriately understandable. Based on the respondents' perspectives, the English language skills that they perceived to have improved were reading and writing skills, especially for the *fun grammar*, reading spot, and exploration components. Utilizing the SEMESTA website as one of the English learning materials can help students learn English independently and feel the benefits of improving their English skills even though it is a gradual process. However, a number of things still need to be developed to optimize the SEMESTA website to support the English Language learning process. First, the content and variety of material on the SEMESTA website need to be improved and supplemented so that the materials are not only dominated by reading and writing exercises but also include video or listening material to help students in improving their productive speaking skills. Also, additional features need to be made to make the website look more attractive. Lastly, a login or sign-up feature must be added to identify who is accessing the website to monitor the student learning process through the SEMESTA website.

KEYWORDS

effectiveness, English, SEMESTA, online learning, website

INTRODUCTION

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 era demands transformations in all aspects of human life, including higher education institutions. Students who live in this era, as users of higher education services, need to be able to live in a dynamic, flexible, often unstructured work environment and use many rapidly evolving information technology in this era (Payne, 2019). With such needs, students are required to develop more soft skills, including the ability to communicate between individuals and within groups, the ability to generate ideas and initiatives as well as innovations to accomplish a mission or solve a problem, collaborate with colleagues that have different skills and characters, and the ability to continue learning even if it is not in a formal setting (lifelong learning). Due to the emergence of these different student needs, higher education institutions are also required to adjust their education system to meet

the students' expectations as future leaders of the next generation and the rapidly changing needs of the industrial world.

The learning process is one aspect of the higher education system that requires adjustment. The learning process amid the current COVID-19 pandemic is expected to be carried out optimally without neglecting the strict implementation of health protocols (PROKES). Universitas Brawijaya (UB), one of the largest universities in East Java, has currently implemented a hybrid learning system to promote achieving more effective learning objectives. During the learning process using the hybrid learning system, some students will participate in online (synchronous) learning using Zoom or the Google Meet application. At the same time, other students are learning offline in class.

In light of this, the Faculty of Vocational Studies has also implemented a hybrid learning system for all courses taught in the Even semester of 2021/2022. One course that implements online and offline learning is English as a General Course (MKU) for Bachelor of Applied (D4) Hospitality Management students. The application of English learning activities as MKU in the second semester includes General English material, which helps improve students' ability to communicate using English in everyday contexts (daily communication), the material on the use of English to communicate in the context of the hospitality industry, and material on TOEFL preparation.

To support the online student learning process, Irmawati and Dewi (2021) have developed teaching materials or Web-based English teaching materials called SEMESTA (Source of English Materials Using Technology-based Application) that can be accessed at <https://semesta.landa.id> as a product of Hibah Penelitian Pemula (HPP). SEMESTA is expected to be able to accommodate students' needs in learning English. Apart from that, students may use these teaching materials independently to learn English related to language rules, and teachers or lecturers may also use them in online learning during this pandemic. A number of studies have been conducted regarding the use of web-based materials in English learning activities. The results from studies by Chen et al. (2004), Rezvani and Ketabi (2011), and Khoiriyah (2020) showed that web-based learning activities could improve students' English skills, increase interaction between students and teachers, and boost student motivation to learn English in the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL).

Although many previous studies have shown positive results on using the web for learning English, there has yet to be research discussing the effectiveness of using SEMESTA in the English learning process for university students. Therefore, further research needs to be conducted to determine how the effectiveness of web-based English materials in SEMESTA can help students improve their English skills during online learning. In other words, this study aims to determine hospitality management students' perspectives on the effectiveness of using SEMESTA to improve their English skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online Learning

Today's technology and information have advanced very rapidly. The application of Information, Communication, and Technology has been carried out in various community services, including in the field of education. In the education field, this is referred to as e-learning. According to Sibagariang (2016), e-learning is a technology-based learning concept, whether it be information technology, telecommunication, or digital. Meanwhile, online learning

has narrower limits where information technology is used, especially the Internet. Thus, online learning can be considered a part of e-learning.

Web-based Learning

Currently, technology and information have developed very rapidly. The application of Information, Communication, and Technology has been carried out in various community services, including in the field of education. In the field of education, this is known as e-learning. According to Sibagariang (2016), e-learning is a technology-based learning concept, whether it be information technology, telecommunication, or digital. Meanwhile, online learning has narrower limits where information technology is used, especially the Internet. Therefore, online learning is part of e-learning. One form of online learning that can be applied in education is web-based learning. Sibagariang (2016) defined web-based learning as a remote learning system based on information technology using a web interface. In regards to the level of interactivity in web-based learning, three types of web-based learning can be used to support the Remote Learning Process (PJJ):

*** Text and Figureic Web-Based Learning**

Text and Figureics are the most basic types of web-based learning programs. In this type, the teaching staff only stores learning materials on the web, and students can access them easily.

*** Interactive Web-Based Learning**

This web-based learning model has a higher level of interactivity than the first model. This model is equipped with learning tools or self-tests, text entry, column matching, and others.

*** Interactive Multimedia Web-Based Learning**

In this type, teaching staff can interact with students in real-time using audio and video streaming, interactive web discussions, and even audio/video desktop conferences. The third model has the highest level of interactivity compared to the others.

Website SEMESTA

The SEMESTA web-based platform, developed in collaboration with a professional team, contains components of learning objectives, vocabulary building, reading spots, grammar infocus, experience points, and rewards (enrichment) for each unit display. Web-based materials that have been developed can be accessed at <https://semesta.landa.id/>. This website is called SEMESTA, which stands for The Source of English Materials using Technology-based Applications, which means the source of English material uses Website technology-based applications (see Figure 2). The SEMESTA Website's home page is dynamic and enables the admin to modify and update the content at any time according to the requirements and updates of information. This website uses the UB website subdomain as the main domain. Therefore, the researcher submits a hosting application to UB to link the SEMESTA website to the Faculty of Vocational Studies of Universitas Brawijaya Education Website.

SEMESTA displays five components in each unit, in which each component will display material that users can directly access. SEMESTA consists of 7 units with different topics: Unit 1: My Account and Social Media, Unit 2: New Normal Activities, Unit 3: Healthy Life, Unit 4: Local Houses, Unit 5: Online Trading, Unit 6: Education, Unit 7: Multicultural Marriage. In each unit, components in the web include learning objectives, vocabulary building, reading spots, grammar in focus, experience points, and rewards (enrichment). The materials are organized on a website called SEMESTA (The Source of English Materials using Technology-based Applications) to facilitate Hybrid Learning.

RESEARCH METHODS

Considering that this research aims to obtain the University of Brawijaya Hospitality Management (MP) study program students' overview or perceptions on using the SEMESTA web, this research used a mixed method approach (mixed method) with embedded design. Embedded design is a mixed methods design in which one data set provides additional support or roles for other types of data in research (Cresswell, Plano Clark, et al., 2003 in Cresswell & Clark, 2007:67).

Figure 1. Embeded design mixed method (Cresswell & Clark, 2007:68)

Respondent

The study's respondents were 35 Management Study Program students from the Faculty of Vocational Studies at Universitas Brawijaya who had used the SEMESTA website for the English Language Learning process in order to improve their English proficiency.

Data Collection Techniques

The data collection instruments used were questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaire is in the form of a Likert Scale (scale of 1 to 4) and essay questions. The questionnaire was first tested to determine its validity and reliability before being used for data collection, and then revision was made due to deficiencies such as the ambiguity of the question items and fill-in instructions. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with students who were reachable by researchers. The interviews included educational topics that were also addressed in the questionnaire. However, they were more in-depth and used a flexible set of questions to go further and deeper into the implementation of this program.

Data Analysis Technique

Questionnaire data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation for each aspect of education, and were presented in tabular form. Data in the form of essays and interviews were analyzed using qualitative data processing techniques as proposed by Miles, Huberman & Saldana (2014) and shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Data Analysis Techniques (Miles et al., 2014)

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' Perspectives on English Learning Materials

The respondents' perspectives on the English learning materials that have been uploaded to SEMESTA web content are used as a parameter to explain the effectiveness of the SEMESTA website as learning materials and media. As shown in Figure 3, many respondents strongly agree with the statement, "The English material presented appropriates with the needs of the respondents," with a total of 10 respondents out of 35 respondents. Then, 14 respondents agree with the statement. Afterward, 11 respondents state that they are neutral to the statement. Lastly, no respondents disagree or strongly disagree with the statement.

Figure 3. The Perspectives of Respondents on the Conformity of English Language Material with the Respondents' needs

Furthermore, based on the data in Figure 4 for the statement "the material presented can be understood easily," it is known that ten respondents strongly agreed with this statement. Then, as many as 20 respondents agree with the statement. Up to 5 respondents give a neutral response to the statement "the material presented can be easily understood." Lastly, neither respondents disagree nor strongly disagree with the statement.

Figure 4. Respondents' Perspectives on the Ease of the offered Materials

According to Figure 5, 10 respondents strongly agree with the statement, "the current materials are required to support English comprehension," while 18 respondents agree. However, seven respondents are neutral about the statement. Lastly, none of the respondents disagree and strongly disagree with the statement.

Figure 5. Respondents' Perspectives on the Current Materials Required to Support English Comprehension

Respondents' Perspectives on Using the SEMESTA Website

Based on the data in Figure 6, nine respondents strongly agree with the statement, "the website that has been made can be easily accessed on all devices." Then, a total of 16 respondents agree with the statement, while seven respondents give neutral responses to the statement, "the website that has been made can be easily accessed on all devices." Finally, two respondents are disagreed, and one respondent are strongly disagreed with the statement.

Figure 6. Respondents' Perspectives on Easily Accessible Website on all Devices

In addition, Figure 7 illustrates that 11 respondents state they strongly agree with the statement, "the website that has been built is attractive and appropriate to user convenience." Meanwhile, nine respondents give a neutral response to the statement, "the website that has been built is attractive and appropriate to user convenience." Then, as many as 12 respondents agree with the statement. However, two respondents disagree, and one respondent strongly disagrees with the statement.

Figure 7. Respondents' Perspectives on SEMESTA Website that is attractive and appropriate to User Convenience

Moreover, Figure 8 shows that seven respondents strongly agreed with the statement, "respondents are more intense in using this website to learn English," while 13 respondents agreed with the statement. Then, 14 respondents give a neutral response to the statement, "respondents are more intense in using this website to learn English," and one respondent disagrees with the statement. Finally, there are no respondents who strongly disagree with the

statement.

Figure 8. Respondents' Perspectives on the High Intensity Use of the SEMESTA Website for the English Learning Process

Respondents' Perspectives on the Role of the SEMESTA Website in Improving English Proficiency

Figure 9 shows that eight respondents say that the SEMESTA website is extremely helpful for improving their English skills. Meanwhile, three respondents state that the SEMESTA website is very helpful in improving their English skills. Next, 20 respondents state that the SEMESTA website is somewhat helpful in improving their English skills. On the other hand, two respondents state that the website is not very helpful, and two respondents give no responses.

Figure 9 Respondents' Perspectives Peran Website SEMEST Respondents' Perspectives on the Role of the SEMESTA Website in Improving English Proficiency

In addition, the Figure 10 shows that four respondents state that the fun grammar part is extremely helpful in learning English. Five respondents say that all sections on the website are very helpful in learning English and 15 respondents state that some of the units on the website are somewhat helpful in learning English. Then, two respondents choose the exploration unit, which is extremely helpful in learning English, while two other respondents choose the reading unit, which is extremely helpful in learning English. Also, two respondents stated that the unit part is extremely helpful in learning English. Lastly, five respondents have yet to give a response.

Figure 10. Respondents' Perspectives on the Most Helpful English Components on the SEMESTA Website in Improving English Proficiency (1: Reading, 2: Fun Grammar, 3 Exploration, 4: Quiz, 5: The website entire features are helpful, 6: Some website features are helpful, 7: No response)

From the respondent's perspectives on the most interesting thing on the website, Figure 11 shows that ten respondents responded that everything on the website is interesting. Four respondents liked the appearance and the button display system, three answered that exploration is the most interesting unit, and three claimed that grammar is an interesting unit. Then, two respondents respond to the speaking section, and two respondents answer the dashboard because it covers the entire website. Meanwhile, two respondents claim that reading material is the most interesting part. On the other hand, two respondents answer that the menu display is the most interesting, one respondent responds that unit 2 is the most interesting, one respondent states that completing the sentence is the most interesting, and one respondent says that survival mode is the most interesting. Lastly, one respondent does not like the appearance, and three respondents do not give any response.

Figure 11. Respondents' Perspectives on the most interesting English Component on the SEMESTA website

Descriptions:

1. Overall been Attractive
2. Appearance and Button Display System
3. *Exploration*
4. *Grammar*
5. *Speaking section*
6. *Dashboard* because it covers the entire *website*
7. *Reading material*
8. *Menu*
9. *Unit 2*
10. Complete the Sentences
11. *Survival mode*
12. Simply dislike the way it looks
13. No response

Respondents experienced an improvement after using the "SEMESTA" website. Figure 12 shows that ten respondents experience an improvement in reading. Seven respondents feel that their writing has improved, and three answered that their listening has improved. Meanwhile, three respondents said that they improved in reading and writing, and two respondents improved in speaking and reading. Lastly, two respondents improved in speaking and writing, two experienced an improvement in all aspects, two improved in listening and reading, one respondent improved in speaking, and three respondents did not feel any improvement.

Figure 12. Respondents' Perspectives on Improved English Language Proficiency after Using the SEMESTA Website

Descriptions:

1. *Reading skill*
2. *Writing skill*
3. *Listening skill*
4. *Reading and Writing skills*
5. *Speaking and Reading skills*
6. *Speaking and Writing skills*
7. Improved in all aspects
8. *Listening and Reading skills*
9. *Speaking skill*
10. No improvements have been made at all.

Suggestions from Respondents to Optimize the SEMESTA Website

Respondents start to perceive an improvement from using this website, but they still have some suggestions on the development of this website. Figure 13 shows that 14 respondents have not given any suggestions since the respondents feel the web has had as much as necessary. Meanwhile, nine respondents suggest the website appearance needs to be improved to make it more attractive, as well as buttons, symbols, collection methods, and the display must be easily understood by respondents who are new to the site. Four respondents suggest improving content related to materials and sample questions as well as interactive content. Three respondents suggest improving website accessibility despite future growth in users' numbers. Then, two respondents suggest adding more features to the website so that users can access it more easily, one respondent suggests more concise material, and one respondent suggests for login or sign-up feature. Lastly, one respondent suggests making submitting answers easier, adding color emphasis on certain words in fun grammar, and combining Learning Objectives with Exploration.

Figure 13. Respondents' Suggestions on the Optimization of the SEMESTA Website

Descriptions:

1. Not required, Somewhat Good.
2. Improved the appearance of the website to make it more attractive, such as buttons, symbols, and collection methods, also the display must be easily understood by respondents who are new to the site.
3. Improved content related to materials and sample questions, and interactive content.
4. Increased website accessibility despite future growth in users' numbers.
5. Adding more features to the website to make it easier for people to access.
6. More concise materials
7. *Log in/sign up*
8. Easy submissions of answers, adding color emphasis on certain words in *fun grammar*, and suggestions for combining Learning Objectives with Exploration.

Discussion

Respondents on English learning materials give positive perspectives since the offered material on the SEMESTA website complies with students' needs so that students may understand the material more optimally and understand English more easily. It is also since web-based learning is developed with the intention of facilitating students' access to learning materials in different forms with a more enjoyable experience (Radovan & Perdih, 2016). In addition, in line with this perspective, the materials displayed on web-based learning are usually also made from a number of credible sources and based on rules from associated institutions or parties (Radovan & Perdih, 2016).

Respondents also give a positive perspective on the use of the SEMESTA website because they find it to be user-friendly, attractive, appropriate to user convenience, which encourage them to use it more to learn English. It is in accordance with Yap's statement (2016) that the use of online learning can boost students' interest in learning the offered material. Yap (2016) also mentioned that online learning often provides an attractive appearance, which makes students feel more enthusiastic about accessing the material.

Respondents also stated that the SEMESTA website helps improve their English proficiency. It is because web-based learning boosts student motivation to learn the material, which gives respondents more opportunities to practice the provided material (Hwang, et al, 2016). It is in line with research conducted by Abou EL-Seoud, et al. (2014) that found students who take e-learning courses provide better learning outcomes than those who take face-to-face lessons or traditional systems. According to Harandi (2015), this can be brought on by a number of factors, such as: 1) e-learning is considered to be student autonomy, 2) e-learning is considered to be a tool for solving student problems, 3) e-learning is considered to multimedia learning, and 4) e-learning in which the teacher serves as a companion.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings lead to the conclusion that the SEMESTA website (Source of English Materials Using a Technology-based Application) as a medium for learning English for Hospitality Management students is easily accessible on all devices. However, website buffering also occurred when respondents used the SEMESTA website. Furthermore, respondents' perspective on English learning materials on the SEMESTA website shows that the material presented complies with their needs and is appropriately understandable. Then, based on the respondent's perspective, the English language skills that they perceive to have improved are reading and writing skills, particularly for the *fun grammar*, reading spot, and exploration components.

Utilizing the SEMESTA website as one of the English learning materials can help students learn English independently and feel the benefits of improving their English skills even though it is a gradual process. However, several elements must be developed to make the most of the SEMESTA website to support the English learning process. First, the content and variety of material on the SEMESTA website need to be improved and supplemented so that the materials are not only dominated by reading and writing exercises but also include video or listening materials to help students in improving their productive speaking skills. Besides, additional features need to be made to make the website look more attractive. Lastly, a log-in or sign-up feature must be added to identify who is accessing the website in order to monitor the student learning process through the SEMESTA website.

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